

“There is a Silver Lining”: Surviving Intimate Partner Violence through the Eyes of Older Women in Arkansas

Jacqueline Burse, PhD

LMSW, School of Social Work, The University of Arkansas at Little Rock, USA

Sederick Rice, PhD

Gerontology Graduate Student, School of Social Work, The University of Arkansas at Little Rock, USA

Suggested Citation

Burse, J., & Rice, S. (2024). “There is a Silver Lining”: Surviving Intimate Partner Violence through the Eyes of Older Women in Arkansas. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 1004-1015.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).84](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).84)

Abstract:

One in four women in the United States report experiencing domestic violence / intimate partner violence (IPV), and nearly 45% of African American/Black women reported experiencing this issue (D’Inverno, et al., 2019). Regrettably, African American/Black women represent 31% of domestic violence fatalities and are more than three times more likely than Caucasian/White women to be killed by an intimate partner.

Violence against women and intimate partner violence (IPV) is a major societal and public health concern nationally and internationally (Costa, & Barros, 2016; Pereira, & Gaspar, 2021; Renner, Whitney, & Vasquez, 2015). IPV is also a global health concern and is occurring increasingly in older (>50+ years of age) populations of women. There are also major gaps in data and knowledge on the intervention and prevention of IPV in older women as well as with reporting.

This study involved interviewing thirteen women over the age of 50 that are from various racial and life experiences, who have experienced intimate partner violence (IPV) in Arkansas. This study seeks to explore not only the prevalence and nature of the abuse but also the coping strategies employed by these women and the support sought.

The findings identified 3 major themes to include resilience and survival, support systems and barriers to accessing help. By focusing on this often-overlooked demographic, this research aims to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of IPV and to highlight the need for tailored interventions that address the specific needs of older women from diverse backgrounds. Through these women’s stories, insight was gained on their resilience and strength, as well as recommendations for systemic changes to better support older women who experience IPV in their journeys towards safety and healing.

Keywords: *Intimate partner violence, older women, help seeking, coping strategies, barriers to support.*

Introduction

Intimate partner violence (IPV), also known as domestic violence (DV), remains a pervasive and profoundly disturbing social issue, affecting individuals across all demographics and life

spans. According to the Center for Disease and Control (Breiding, Chen, & Black, 2010). while much of the existing research has focused on younger populations, there is a growing need to understand the experiences of older adults who face IPV. Intimate partner violence leads to

physical injuries, mental health concerns, and sometimes even death. This is not an issue that discriminates among gender, socioeconomic class, sexual orientation, or race. However, the intersectionality of oppressed identities, experienced by African American women, place them at a higher risk of experiencing DV, and in 1998 was the leading cause of death among African American women from ages 15-34 (Watlington, & Murphy, 2006). In Arkansas, a state characterized by its rich cultural heritage and diverse population, IPV continues to be a significant public health concern. Older women often face unique challenges and barriers when dealing with IPV, including generational attitudes towards gender roles, potential isolation, and health concerns that can be exacerbated by abuse. Furthermore, the intersectionality of race and ethnicity can compound these challenges, influencing both the experience of IPV and the resources available for support and recovery.

Literature Review

Violence against women and intimate partner violence (IPV) is a major societal and public health concern nationally and internationally (Dichter, et al., 2020; Gerino, et al., 2018; Sanz-Barbero, Barón, & Vives-Cases, 2019; Waller, & Bent-Goodley, 2023; Zink, et al., 2005). IPV refers to “any type of abusive behavior (e.g., emotional, verbal, physical, sexual) that occurs between intimate partners, such as spouses, those living in a common-law relationship, or in a dating relationship” (Weeks, et al., 2021). IPV is often associated with gender violence and has been recognized as a serious violation of women’s human rights internationally and is addressed differently in young adult and older populations of women (Sanz-Barbero, Barón, & Vives-Cases, 2019; Weeks, et al., 2021; Crockett, Brandl, & Dabby, 2015; Giraldo-Rodríguez, & Agudelo-Botero, 2024; Gomez-Casillas, Lozano, & Rentería, 2021; Irene-López, & Kalmakis, 2023; Makaroun, et al., 2020; Ojifinni, Maposa, & Ibisomi, 2021; Parnell, Lacey, & Wood, 2022).

IPV often starts early and continues throughout people’s lives (Dichter, et al., 2020), and

according to the National Intimate Partner and Sexual Violence Survey “among female victims who experienced contact sexual violence, physical violence, and/or stalking by an intimate partner in their lifetime, more than 70% (72.3% or 42.7 million) reported that their first victimization by an intimate partner occurred before age 25” (Leemis, et al., 2022). Unfortunately, IPV is often only studied as an issue for young adolescent and adult women between the ages of 15 and 46, but there is an increasing emphasis and data collection effort to highlight the long-term and harmful psychological, emotional, physical health, and financial effects of IPV in older women (Dichter, et al., 2020; Gerino, et al., 2018; Sanz-Barbero, Barón, & Vives-Cases, 2019; Zink, et al., 2005; Weeks, et al., 2021; Cations, et al., 2022; Khurana, & Loder, 2022; Yılmaz, et al., 2023).

It is also important to understand that historically, IPV in older women may have been categorized as elder abuse, which makes it difficult to accurately capture experiences of these women in the right context, and that data typically comes from disclosures to physicians and healthcare workers when reported (Zink, et al., 2005; Giraldo-Rodríguez, & Agudelo-Botero, 2024; Khurana, & Loder, 2022). For example, older adults experience a myriad of physical, spiritual and emotional challenges of aging that impacts their well-being (Yılmaz, et al., 2023). Currently, there are no valid and reliable screening tool in primary care settings to identify IPV in older and vulnerable adult women however, findings indicate that risk factors for IPV in older women include age, parental violence and intergenerational transmission of violence, low social support and isolation from their community, cognitive impairment, depressive symptoms, ethnic differences, life stress, living with an abusive partner, verbal abuse, substance abuse (Curry, et al., 2018). Preventive strategies to reduce IPV in older women is typically supported by educational initiatives and referrals to supportive services, but barriers such as “victims’ feelings of shame and embarrassment, feeling comfortable and safe to share details of IPV, threats to privacy and/or safety, and data indicates that middle-

aged women may be less prepared to respond to screening questions and have not been acculturated to address IPV in healthcare settings (Dichter, et al., 2020).

African American women experience domestic violence/IPV at rate that is 35% higher than the rate of Caucasian/White women and there is a missing gap of research data and information on the relationship between domestic violence/IPV for older women in intimate partner relationships due to reporting variations of elder abuse, neglect, and mistreatment (Crockett, Brandl, & Dabby, 2015; Khurana, & Loder, 2022; Burse, et al., 2022). One study explored the impact of IPV on mental health outcomes, coping and protective mechanism of mental health in African American and Caribbean black women populations and found that social support is key to coping and “cultural notions of strength were linked to generations of African-heritage women who had overcome multiple forms of adversity” (Parnell, Lacey, & Wood, 2022).

In a similar study, Burse, et al. (2024) utilized a qualitative interpretive meta-synthesis (QIMS) of older African American women’s experience with IPV and found that coping mechanisms and empowerment, faith and spirituality and personal resilience and a strong sense of identity supported overcoming adversity (p. 6).

The literature also highlighted data on cultural and geographical differences in older women populations, who experience IPV in the United States and around the world. A study conducted by Giraldo-Rodríguez, & Agudelo-Botero (2024) examined elder abuse experienced by older Mexican women with disabilities and found that the “prevalence of elder abuse among women with functional limitations and disabilities is higher than among men with the same characteristics” (p. 94). Furthermore, Gomez-Casillas, Lozano, & Rentería, (2021) analyzed the burden of IPV in women during their midlife years in 151 countries and found that in Africa, women are expected to suffer from IPV for 6 years, 11.4 years in the Democratic Republic of Congo, 8 years in Equatorial Guinea, Zambia, Ethiopia, Liberia,

South Sudan, and Uganda, 2.6 years in South and North America, 4.3 years in Asia, and 1.7 years in Europe (p. 3). Prevalence data studies also found that certain central African countries have the highest prevalence rates of IPV and Years expected to Live with Intimate Partner Violence (YLIPV) (p. 4).

Finally, Irene-López, & Kalmakis, (2023) conducted a hermeneutic and phenomenological study in Puerto Rico in women over 60 and found that women in the study were heavily influenced by Puerto Rican culture, “persistence violence in their lives leads to significant mental and physical health consequences” and “older women shared a belief that “machismo” or aggressive masculine pride enabled IPV” (p. 1349). The study also found that “religion promoted an atmosphere of trust and honesty women needed to support leaving the abusive relationship,” and the “fear of the abuser and dependence on social and cultural norms explained by women did not seek help for years” (pp. 1349-1350).

Methods

Participants

These interviews involved thirteen women over the age of 50 that was extrapolated from a larger study who experienced intimate partner violence (IPV) in Arkansas. Participants were recruited through local domestic violence agencies, support groups, and healthcare providers that work with IPV survivors. The selection criteria included: (1) being a woman aged 50 or older, (2) having experienced IPV, and (3) residing in Arkansas. Efforts were made to ensure a diverse sample in terms of race and ethnicity to capture a wide range of experiences.

Data Collection

Data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews conducted between October 2019 and May 2020. Each interview lasted between 60 to 90 minutes and was conducted in a private setting to ensure confidentiality for each participant. The interviews were guided by an interview protocol

that included open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed narratives about their experiences of IPV, coping strategies, and support systems.

Interview Procedure

The interview process and procedures highlighted five critical areas:

1. **Demographic Information:** Age, race/ethnicity, education, employment status, and relationship status.
2. **Experiences of IPV:** Type and range of abuse, effect on physical and mental health, and causes or patterns of abusive behaviors.
3. **Survival Strategies:** Approaches used to survive IPV, including seeking and support, internal resilience, and the various protective actions explored.
4. **Support Structures:** The accessibility and efficiency of formal and informal support systems, such as faith-based resources, family, friends, communal resources, and healthcare services.
5. **Identifying Barriers to Support:** Systemic challenges to include cultural, economic, and societal barriers.

Data Analysis

All interviews were audio-recorded with the participants' consent and transcribed verbatim. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. The analysis process involved several steps:

1. **Familiarization:** Reading and re-reading transcripts to become deeply immersed with the data and gain understanding of individual experiences.
2. **Coding:** Identifying and labeling relevant characteristics of the transcript that captured important aspects of the participants' experiences.

3. **Theme Development:** Linking codes into larger themes that represented patterns in the data.

4. **Reviewing Themes:** Sifting themes to ensure they precisely reflected the data and were lucid.

5. **Defining and Naming Themes:** Clearly defining what each theme encompassed and naming them to reflect their essence.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the University of Arkansas at Little Rock Institutional Review Board. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their participation. Participants were assured of their anonymity and confidentiality, and they were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Each participant received a \$25 gift card for their participation. Pseudonyms were used in the transcripts and in the reporting of the findings to protect participants' identities.

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the experiences of older women from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds in Arkansas, it is not without limitations. The small sample size and the specific geographic focus may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, self-reporting may introduce recall bias. Despite these limitations, the study offers important contributions to the understanding of IPV among older women.

Results

Table 1. Demographics of Each Participant

Name	Race/Ethnicity	Education	Employment Status	Relationship Status	Age	Types of Abuse
Barbara	African American	HS Diploma	Full-time Employment	Married	53	Physical/Verbal/Financial

Betty	African American	Associates Degree	Caregiver	Married	56	Physical/Verbal/Sexual
Shirley	African American	GED	Volunteer	Married	62	Physical/Emotional
Caren	African American	Bachelor's Degree	Retired	Single	64	Physical/Verbal/Financial/Sexual
Donna	African American	Master's Degree	Retired	Divorced	68	Emotional/Physical/Sexual
Johnny Mae	African American	GED	Volunteer	Separated	70	Physical/Verbal/Financial
Thelma	African American	HS Diploma	Retired	Married	73	Emotional
Lucy	Caucasian	Master's Degree	Part-time	Separated	53	Physical/Verbal/Financial
Margret	Caucasian	HS Diploma	Part-time	Married	56	Emotional/Sexual
Sandy	Caucasian	Associate Degree	Retired	Divorced	61	Physical/Emotional
Regina	Caucasian	Bachelor's Degree	Retired	Divorced	63	Physical/Verbal/Financial
Blanche	Caucasian	Associate Degree	Part-time	Single	65	Emotional/Financial
Claire	Caucasian	HS Diploma	Retired	Married	67	Physical/Verbal

Note: *Pseudo names were provided to protect the confidentiality of each participant

Table 2. Major Themes

Major Themes
Resilience & Survival
Support Systems
Barriers to Accessing Help

Demographic Characteristics

The thirteen participants in this study ranged in age from 53 to 73 years of age. The sample included women from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds: seven African American and six Caucasian. Participants varied in terms of education and employment status, with some having completed higher education and others having only a high school diploma. Employment statuses included retired, employed, and unemployed.

Various Types Intimate Partner Violence

Types of Abuse

Participants reported experiencing various types of IPV, including physical, emotional, psychological, and financial abuse. Physical abuse was reported by ten participants and included acts such as hitting, choking, and

pushing. Six of the participants reported emotional and 7 experienced verbal abuse. All participants shared behaviors such as constant criticism, humiliation, threats, and controlling behaviors, however some did not identify them as types of abuse. Financial abuse, reported by six participants, included control over financial resources and preventing access to money.

Duration and Impact

The duration of abuse varied among participants, with some experiencing IPV for several years and others for decades. The impact of IPV on physical health included injuries such as bruises, broken bones, and chronic pain. Mental health impacts included depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and feelings of worthlessness. Many participants also reported that the abuse had negatively affected their self-esteem and overall well-being.

Coping Strategies

Personal Resilience

Despite the severe impact of IPV, participants demonstrated considerable resilience. Many women relied on their inner strength and faith to

cope with the abuse. Strategies included maintaining a sense of hope, engaging in prayer or spiritual practices, and focusing on their love for their children or grandchildren as a source of motivation to endure and eventually leave the abusive relationship.

Seeking Help

Participants utilized a variety of strategies to seek help. Nine women sought assistance from family and friends, though the support they received varied. Six participants accessed community resources such as shelters, counseling services, and support groups. Legal measures, such as restraining orders, were pursued by four women. However, participants noted that seeking help was often hindered by fear of retaliation, shame, and cultural or generational stigmas associated with leaving a partner.

Support Systems

Formal Support

Formal support systems, such as domestic violence shelters, counseling services, and healthcare providers, played a critical role for many participants. Women who accessed these services reported that they provided essential resources, including safe housing, emotional support, and legal assistance. However, some participants faced challenges in accessing these services, such as long wait times, lack of culturally sensitive services, and geographic barriers in rural areas.

Informal Support

Informal support from family, friends, and faith communities was crucial for many participants. Ten women reported receiving emotional and practical support from their close social networks. However, the extent and nature of support varied, with some women experiencing judgment or disbelief when they disclosed their abuse. Participants emphasized the importance of having a trusted confidant and the role of community solidarity in their journey toward recovery.

Barriers to Support

Participants identified several barriers to accessing support, including:

1. Cultural and Generational Factors:

Participants shared how cultural norms and generational attitudes towards marriage and gender roles supported patriarchal views and women seeking help or leaving their abusive partners were discouraged. Some participants felt pressured to keep family matters private and maintain the presence of a healthy home environment.

2. Economic Dependence:

Many survivors shared the stress of being financially dependent on their abusive partners post a barrier to leaving. Many participants shared how they lacked the financial resources to leave the relationship and support themselves and their children independently.

3. Lack of Awareness:

Education and a lack of awareness about available resources and legal rights hindered some women from seeking help. Participants expressed the need for better outreach, education, and financial resources concerning IPV.

4. Healthcare Barriers:

Inadequate access to healthcare, particularly in some of the rural areas, prevented some participants from receiving necessary medical and behavioral health care. Additionally, some women reported negative experiences with healthcare providers who lacked training in identifying and responding to IPV.

Themes

Three overall themes emerged from the analysis of the interviews: Resilience and Survival, Support Systems, and Barriers to Accessing Help.

Resilience and Survival: Despite the severe and prolonged abuse, participants demonstrated remarkable resilience and survival strategies. For example, Thelma shared:

"I had to find my own strength within me that I did not know I had. There were days and many nights I didn't think I could go on, but some way, somehow, I did. I found ways to cope, little by little, day by day."

"I learned to be smarter in my thinking and resources. Although he controlled all the money,

I found ways to save a little here and there. I would hide it and just patiently wait for that moment before I could leave." - Barbara

The abuse was unimaginable, but I knew I couldn't let it continue to break my soul. I started volunteering at the local food pantry, which gave me a sense of determination and a reason to keep going." - Johnny Mae

When I got to my lowest point and fell, I got back up. It was a struggle but I told myself that I had to survive for my children, and for me. They were the strength I needed when I had none." - Caren

"I took up sewing. It might seem small, but having something to focus on, something I could create, it helped me escape, even if just mentally, from the abuse." - Shirley

I started going to therapy secretly at church. Talking to someone helped me understand that I wasn't alone, and that gave me the strength to endure and ultimately come up with my escape plan." -Lucy

I would listen to stories of other women who survived. Their stories encouraged me and gave me hope. that I could survive too, that there was hope for everyday and I held on to it."

-Regina

Support Systems: Both formal and informal support networks were vital in the participants' journeys toward safety and recovery. -Betty

"My sister was my rock. She always checked in on me, and when things got really bad, she was the one who helped me find a safe place to stay."-Caren

"The women's shelter saved my life. They gave me a safe place to stay and connected me with resources I never knew existed." - Blanche

"My neighbor noticed the signs and offered to help. She would keep an eye on the house and let me know if she saw him around when he wasn't supposed to be there." -Sandy

"The support group meetings were a lifeline. Hearing other women's stories and knowing I wasn't alone gave me the strength to keep going."- Margret

"The local church community was incredibly supportive. They offered me not only spiritual guidance but also practical help like food and clothing." - Shirley

"I finally confided in my best friend. She was shocked but immediately supportive, helping me plan my escape and even driving me to appointments." - Lucy

"The counselor I saw at the community center was amazing. She helped me understand my worth and guided me through the legal process to get a restraining order."- Betty

"When I reached out to a domestic violence hotline, the person on the other end was so understanding and patient. They helped me see that I had options and supported me through the initial steps of leaving." - Sandy

"My children were my biggest supporters. They encouraged me to leave and helped me believe that we could have a better life without the abuse." - Barbara

Barriers to Accessing Help: Multiple barriers, including cultural, economic, and systemic factors, hindered participants from accessing necessary support. -Regina

"I didn't know where to turn. The shelters were full, and I couldn't find any information about other resources. It felt like there was no help available for me."-Thelma

"I was too ashamed to ask for help. I felt like people would judge me or blame me for the abuse, so I kept it to myself for a long time."- Johnny Mae

"The closest shelter was hours away, and I didn't have the money or transportation to get there. "I tried to reach out to the police, but they didn't take my situation seriously. It felt like my concerns were dismissed because of my age and background." -Caren

"I was afraid of losing my job if I took time off to go to counseling or attend support groups. The fear of financial instability kept me from seeking the help I needed."- Sandy

"The legal system was overwhelming. I couldn't navigate the paperwork and didn't have the

money for a lawyer. It felt like the system was stacked against me." - Regina

"I faced discrimination at the local social services office. They didn't seem to understand my needs or the urgency of my situation because of my age." - Thelma

"My partner kept all the money, and I was completely dependent on him. I couldn't afford to leave or pay for any services, so I felt trapped with no options." - Lucy

I was told that the services were only for younger women or that my situation wasn't severe enough to qualify for assistance. It made me feel like my problems didn't matter."

-Barbara

"Lack of understanding made it difficult for me to get information. I didn't know what services were available or how to access them because the resources weren't in terms I could understand."-Margret

Discussion

Resilience and Survival

The narratives of the 13 women interviewed reveal a profound sense of resilience and survival. Despite the traumatic experiences of intimate partner violence (IPV), these women demonstrated remarkable strength and adaptability. Their stories reflect not only their ability to endure and overcome adversity but also their capacity to rebuild their lives. This resilience is consistent with existing literature, which underscores the inherent strength and coping strategies of survivors of IPV (Woods-Giscombe, et al., 2023). It is crucial to acknowledge and amplify these stories of resilience, as they provide valuable insights into the ways older women navigate and survive IPV.

Support Systems

A recurring theme in the interviews was the critical role of support systems. Many women highlighted the importance of social networks, including family, friends, and community organizations, in their journey towards recovery. These support systems provided emotional,

practical, and sometimes financial assistance, which were pivotal in helping them leave abusive situations and rebuild their lives. However, the effectiveness of these support systems varied significantly. While some women received robust support, others faced skepticism or stigmatization, which hindered their ability to seek help. This finding aligns with previous studies, which emphasize the mixed impact of social support on IPV survivors (Johnson, & Zlotnick, 2009).

Barriers to Accessing Services

Despite the availability of various services, the women in this study encountered numerous barriers when attempting to access help. These barriers included limited awareness of available services, geographic isolation, financial constraints, and fear of retaliation. Additionally, age-specific challenges, such as mobility issues and health concerns, further complicated their ability to seek assistance. The intersectionality of age and IPV creates unique challenges that are often overlooked in service provision. To improve access, it is essential for service providers to adopt a more nuanced approach that considers the specific needs of older IPV survivors.

Implications for Policy and Practice

The findings of this study have several implications for policy and practice. Firstly, there is a need for increased awareness and targeted outreach to inform older women about available services and support. Policymakers and service providers should also consider developing specialized programs that address the unique challenges faced by older IPV survivors. Furthermore, enhancing the training of professionals who work with IPV survivors can help in recognizing and addressing the specific needs of this demographic. By implementing these changes, it is possible to create a more supportive and effective environment for older women who experience IPV.

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the experiences of older women survivors of IPV, from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds

in Arkansas, it is not without limitations. The small sample size and the specific geographic focus may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, self-reporting may introduce recall bias. Despite these limitations, the study offers important contributions to the understanding of IPV among older women from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds in Arkansas.

IPV is often studied in younger women, but in this study victims of IPV in Arkansas, over 50 years of age, represented a unique group to study because they were varied in their levels of education and employment, and from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds. The study utilized in-depth structured interviews to capture the experiences of older women who experienced IPV, and to understand their coping strategies and the role of their support systems. Women in the study reported experiences with physical, emotional, psychological, and financial abuse with varying timeframes from several years to decades. Older women who experience IPV are often more vulnerable to the long-term effects of that abuse, especially if they suffer from underlining physical disabilities and mental health conditions, due to aging (Cations, et al., 2022; Khurana, & Loder, 2022), which often manifests into long-term physical, and mental health ailments.

In this study, the women reported experiencing depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), feelings of worthlessness and diminished self-esteem and a sense of overall well-being. Findings highlighted their personal resilience, ability to seek help from community resources, and the value of their formal and informal support systems, which provided some protection (Gerino, et al., 2018). Several themes emerged including participants' resilience and survival skills, the value of informal and formal support networks which supported their safety and recovery, and barriers (cultural, economic, and systemic factors) that often-limited help seeking and successful access to support. Some of the major barriers for many women in this study, was the lack of education and understanding by healthcare providers to provide support to victims of IPV, especially in

rural areas, where there was a lack of cultural awareness and geographic barriers, which limited the availability of resources.

There are several future research implications gained from this study, as it relates to how older women survivors of IPV, from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds in Arkansas find safety and healing, as it relates to a) how informal and formal support groups can strengthen coping strategies, resilience, and financial resources of survivors of IPV, b) more attention to an often over looked demographic and a focus on tailoring interventions that are culturally competent and accessible, c) development of strategies to guide recommendations for systemic changes to help healthcare providers in rural areas identify risk factors for IPV in older women, and d) older women that experience IPV may appear to exhibit more resilience than younger women and may be coping with abuse for longer periods of time, but they are still at high-risk for long-term physical, emotional, and psychological effects, which even in recovery can impact their quality of life into their golden years.

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the experiences of older women survivors of IPV, from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds in Arkansas, it is not without limitations. The small sample size and the specific geographic focus may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, self-reporting may introduce recall bias. Despite these limitations, the study offers important contributions to the understanding of IPV among older women from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds in Arkansas. Future research could expand on this work by including a larger and more diverse sample of older women from different regions. Additionally, longitudinal studies could provide a deeper understanding of the long-term impacts of IPV on older women and the effectiveness of various interventions over time.

Conclusion

IPV is often studied in younger women, but in this study victims of IPV in Arkansas, over 50 years of age, represented a unique group to study because they were varied in their levels of education and employment, and from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds. The study utilized in-depth structured interviews to capture the experiences of older women who experienced IPV, and to understand their coping strategies and the role of their support systems. Women in the study reported experiences with physical, emotional, psychological, and financial abuse with varying timeframes from several years to decades. Older women who experience IPV are often more vulnerable to the long-term effects of that abuse, especially if they suffer from underlining physical disabilities and mental health conditions, due to aging (Cations, et al., 2022; Khurana, & Loder, 2022), which often manifests into long-term physical, and mental health ailments.

In this study, the women reported experiencing depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), feelings of worthlessness and diminished self-esteem and a sense of overall well-being. Findings highlighted their personal resilience, ability to seek help from community resources, and the value of their formal and informal support systems, which provided some protection (Gerino, et al., 2018). Several themes emerged including participants' resilience and survival skills, the value of informal and formal support networks which supported their safety and recovery, and barriers (cultural, economic, and systemic factors) that often-limited help seeking and successful access to support. Some of the major barriers for many women in this study, was the lack of education and understanding by healthcare providers to provide support to victims of IPV, especially in rural areas, where there was a lack of cultural awareness and geographic barriers, which limited the availability of resources.

There are several future research implications gained from this study, as it relates to how older women survivors of IPV, from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds in Arkansas find safety and healing, as it relates to a) how informal and formal support groups can strengthen coping

strategies, resilience, and financial resources of survivors of IPV, b) more attention to an often over looked demographic and a focus on tailoring interventions that are culturally competent and accessible, c) development of strategies to guide recommendations for systemic changes to help healthcare providers in rural areas identify risk factors for IPV in older women, and d) older women that experience IPV may appear to exhibit more resilience than younger women and may be coping with abuse for longer periods of time, but they are still at high-risk for long-term physical, emotional, and psychological effects, which even in recovery can impact their quality of life into their golden years.

References

- Breiding, M. J., Chen, J., & Black, M. C. (2010). *Intimate Partner Violence In the United States – 2010*. Centers for Disease Control.
- Burse, J., McElwee, T. M., Heldman, E., & Campbell, H. B. (2024). Unveiling the Silent Struggle: Exploring Intimate Partner Violence among Older African American Women: A Qualitative Interpretive Meta-Synthesis (QIMS).
- Burse, J., Voth-Schrag, R., Fields, N. L., & Woody, D. (2022). Domestic Violence Survivorship Among a Sample of Older African American Women: An Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(23–24), NP22000–NP22025. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08862605211066541>
- Cations, M., Keage, H. A. D., Laver, K. E., Byles, J., & Loxton, D. (2022). Intimate Partner Violence and Risk for Mortality and Incident Dementia in Older Women. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(5–6), NP2605–NP2625. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520943712>
- Costa, D., & Barros, H. (2016). Instruments to Assess Intimate Partner Violence: A Scoping Review of the Literature. *Violence and Victims*, 31(4), 591–621. <https://doi.org/10.1891/0886-6708.VV-D-14-00122>

- Crockett, C., Brandl, B., & Dabby, F. C. (2015). Survivors in the Margins: The Invisibility of Violence Against Older Women. *Journal of Elder Abuse & Neglect*, 27(4–5), 291–302. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08946566.2015.1090361>
- Curry, S. J., Krist, A. H., Owens, D. K., Barry, M. J., Caughey, A. B., Davidson, K. W., Doubeni, C. A., Epling, J. W. Jr., Grossman, D. C., Kemper, A. R., Kubik, M., Kurth, A., Landefeld, C. S., Mangione, C. M., Silverstein, M., Simon, M. A., Tseng, C. W., & Wong, J. B. (2018). Screening for Intimate Partner Violence, Elder Abuse, and Abuse of Vulnerable Adults: US Preventive Services Task Force Final Recommendation Statement. *JAMA*, 320(16), 1678–1687. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2018.14741>
- D’Inverno, A., Smith, S., Zhang, X., & Chen, J. (2019). *The Impact of Intimate Partner Violence: A 2015 NISVS Research-in-Brief*. National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (U.S.). Retrieved from <https://stacks.cdc.gov/view/cdc/137398>
- Dichter, M. E., Makaroun, L., Tuepker, A., True, G., Montgomery, A. E., & Iverson, K. (2020). Middle-aged Women’s Experiences of Intimate Partner Violence Screening and Disclosure: “It’s a private matter. It’s an embarrassing situation.” *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 35(9), 2655–2661. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-020-05947-3>
- Gerino, E., Caldarrera, A. M., Curti, L., Brustia, P., & Rollè, L. (2018). Intimate Partner Violence in the Golden Age: Systematic Review of Risk and Protective Factors. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 1595. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01595>
- Giraldo-Rodríguez, L., & Agudelo-Botero, M. (2024). Elder abuse experienced by older Mexican women with disabilities: A current and retrospective view on domestic violence. *Journal of Elder Abuse & Neglect*, 36(2), 93–116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08946566.2023.2297224>
- Gomez-Casillas, A., Lozano, M., & Rentería, E. (2021). Expected years lived with intimate partner violence: A new approach for public health. *Global Health Action*, 14(1), 1976442. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16549716.2021.1976442>
- Irene-López, L., & Kalmakis, K. A. (2023). The experience of IPV among older women in Puerto Rico; a hermeneutic phenomenological study. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 79(4), 1342–1352. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15228>
- Johnson, D. M., & Zlotnick, C. (2009). HOPE for battered women with PTSD in domestic violence shelters. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, 40(3), 234–241. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012519>
- Khurana, B., & Loder, R. T. (2022). Injury Patterns and Associated Demographics of Intimate Partner Violence in Older Adults Presenting to U.S. Emergency Departments. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(17–18), NP16107–NP16129. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08862605211022060>
- Leemis, R., Friar, N., Khatiwada, S., Chen, M. S., Kresnow, M., Smith, S. G., Caslin, S., & Basile, K. C. (2022). The National Intimate Partner and Sexual Violence Survey: 2016/2017 Report on Intimate Partner Violence. National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (U.S.). Retrieved from <https://stacks.cdc.gov/view/cdc/124646>
- Makaroun, L. K., Brignone, E., Rosland, A.-M., & Dichter, M. E. (2020). Association of Health Conditions and Health Service Utilization With Intimate Partner Violence Identified via Routine Screening Among Middle-Aged and Older Women. *JAMA Network Open*, 3(4), e203138. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.3138>
- Ojifinni, O., Maposa, I., & Ibisomi, L. (2021). Bayesian semi-parametric spatial modelling of intimate partner violence in Namibia using 2013 Demographic Health Survey Data. *BMC Women’s Health*, 21(1), 286. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-021-01421-2>
- Parnell, R. N., Lacey, K. K., & Wood, M. (2022). Coping and Protective Factors of Mental Health: An Examination of African American and US Caribbean Black Women Exposed to IPV from

a Nationally Representative Sample. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(22), 15343.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192215343>

Pereira, M. U. L., & Gaspar, R. S. (2021). Socioeconomic Factors Associated With Reports of Domestic Violence in Large Brazilian Cities. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 623185.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.623185>

Renner, L. M., Whitney, S. D., & Vasquez, M. (2015). Individual and Interpersonal Risk Factors for Physical Intimate Partner Violence Perpetration by Biological Sex and Ethnicity. *Violence and Victims*, 30(1), 97–119.

<https://doi.org/10.1891/0886-6708.VV-D-13-00123>

Sanz-Barbero, B., Barón, N., & Vives-Cases, C. (2019). Prevalence, associated factors and health impact of intimate partner violence against women in different life stages. *PLOS ONE*, 14(10), e0221049.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0221049>

Waller, B. Y., & Bent-Goodley, T. B. (2023). “I Have to Fight to Get Out”: African American Women Intimate Partner Violence Survivors’ Construction of Agency. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 38(3–4), 4166–4188.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/08862605221113008>

Watlington, C. G., & Murphy, C. M. (2006). The roles of religion and spirituality among African American survivors of domestic violence. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 62(7), 837–857.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.20268>

Weeks, L. E., Stilwell, C., Gagnon, D., Dupuis-Blanchard, S., MacQuarrie, C., & Jackson, L. A. (2021). Initiatives to Support Older Women Who Experience Intimate Partner Violence. *Violence Against Women*, 27(15–16), 3011–3029.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801220988355>

Woods-Giscombe, C. L., Williams, K. P., Conklin, J., Dodd, A., Bravo, L., Anderson, A. M., ... & Hood, D. B. (2023). A scoping review of the concept of resilience among African American women. *Archives of Psychiatric Nursing*, 46, 107–120.

Yılmaz, S., Gunay, E., Lee, D. H., Whiting, K., Silver, K., Koyuturk, M., & Karakurt, G. (2023). Adverse health correlates of intimate partner violence against older women: Mining electronic health records. *PLOS ONE*, 18(3), e0281863.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281863>

Zink, T., Fisher, B. S., Regan, S., & Pabst, S. (2005). The prevalence and incidence of intimate partner violence in older women in primary care practices. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 20(10), 884–888.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1525-1497.2005.0191.x>